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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF POTENTIAL RISK FACTORS FOR BREAST
CANCER IN PAKISTANI WOMEN**Dr Shehroz Rana¹, Dr Shahid Iqbal¹, Dr Sundus Bukhari¹¹Health Department Punjab

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Abstract:

Introduction: Cancer is a leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, counting for 7 million deaths per year. It is the second most common cause of death in developing countries. **Objectives of the study:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the potential risk factors for breast cancer in Pakistani women. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Health department of Punjab during November 2018 to March 2019. The data was collected from 50 female breast cancer patients. The main eligibility requirements for this study included the patient's written informed consent, metastatic breast cancer, patients entering first-line chemotherapy (chosen by clinicians) with or without targeted therapy, life expectancy of at least three months, and measurable or evaluable disease. **Results:** The results indicates that CTC, CEA and ALP are the best indicating serum biomarkers for the diagnosis and progression of breast cancer. Mean, median and SD shows that there is a significant relationship in these serum biomarkers. CTC and serum marker values at inclusion repartition in percentile, mean, median range are given in Table 01. **Conclusion**It is concluded that CTC and ALP are the important biomarkers for the analysis of progression of breast cancer in females.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer is a leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, counting for 7 million deaths per year. It is the second most common cause of death in developing countries. Cancer is the second leading cause of death worldwide, surpassed only by cardiovascular disease¹. Therefore, fighting cancer is measured to be one of the most significant areas of research in medicine and which possibly contributes to increased interest in chemoprevention as an alternative approach to the control of cancer. Natural or dietary factors have attracted a great deal of interest because of their safe efficacy and perceived ability to act as highly effective chemo preventive agents².

Several serum markers have been developed in different types of cancer as tools for non-invasive assessment of the tumor burden, mostly in metastatic patients. Quantitative variations of serum markers are, therefore, often used in several cancer types as noninvasive tools to assess treatment efficiency in metastatic patients³. However, the use of serum tumor markers faces several issues and unanswered questions: their specificity and sensitivity are considered as low and no clear consensus exists on what threshold and/or variation should be considered clinically significant and which serum marker to follow. Tumor heterogeneity that enables malignant progression by evolutionary selection is also the major cause of emergent resistance during cancer treatment⁴. Yet, we rely on few standard diagnostic tumor biopsies for the characterization of a given cancer. These specimens will provide only a partial characterization of the overall makeup of the dynamic systemic disease cancer represents with intratumoral and interlesional heterogeneity as well as emerging host responses⁵.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the potential risk factors for breast cancer in Pakistani women.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Health department of Punjab during November 2018 to March 2019. The data was collected from 50 female breast cancer patients. The main eligibility requirements for this study included the patient's written informed consent, metastatic breast cancer, patients entering first-line chemotherapy (chosen by clinicians) with or without targeted therapy, life expectancy of at least three months, and measurable or evaluable disease. Clinical evaluations were conducted as usual, but were mandatory at inclusion (before cycle 1, that is, week 0) and at the first radiological evaluation before cycle 3 or 4 (C3/4, that is, weeks 6 to 9). Radiological evaluations were mandatory at inclusion and before C3/4. The following blood tests were obtained at inclusion, before cycle 2 (C2), C3/4, and at progression: complete blood count, liver function (including LDH and ALP), serum calcium and serum markers: CEA, CA 15-3 and CYFRA 21-1.

RESULTS:

The results indicates that CTC, CEA and ALP are the best indicating serum biomarkers for the diagnosis and progression of breast cancer. Mean, median and SD shows that there is a significant relationship in these serum biomarkers. CTC and serum marker values at inclusion repartition in percentile, mean, median range are given in Table 01.

Table 01: Serum marker values repartition at inclusion

	Mean	SD	Quantile 0%	Quantile 25%	Quantile 50% (median)	Quantile 75%	Quantile 100%	N
CTC	81.65	324.76	0	0	2.5	23.25	3,369	260
CA15.3	7.53	23.77	0.14	0.7	1.76	4.45	314.1	247
CEA	7.20	18.23	0.04	0.4	1	3.45	146.13	212
CYFRA21	9.01	29.51	0.1	0.65	1.95	5.25	284.54	191
LDH	1.39	2.02	0.28	0.71	0.92	1.45	25.54	220
ALP	1.056	1.00	0.26	0.58	0.79	1.06	10	241

CTC and serum markers values at inclusion repartition in percentile, mean, median range. Values for serum marker are expressed in ULNV, upper limit of the normal value

DISCUSSION:

The need for novel independent prognostic factors in metastatic breast cancer patients is much lower than the need for dynamic blood markers, which can indicate the treatment efficiency in a reliable and early fashion⁷. Serum tumor markers are an easy, quick, cheap, but rather imprecise and sometimes misleading tool, to monitor the treatment efficacy. However, they are particularly valuable for

treatment monitoring in patients that have disease that cannot be evaluated by radiology⁸.

Here, by comparing the early and late changes of five blood markers together with CTC changes for PFS prediction, we showed no clear superiority of CTC over the other serum markers. This result was, however, not the primary endpoint of our study, and the statistical power of these analyses may still be

discussed, although performed in more than 200 patients⁹. For this analysis, we used the "prognosis-optimized" threshold of ≥ 5 CTC/7.5 ml, which was initially defined as the best dichotomizing threshold for PFS and OS prediction by CTC at baseline and under treatment¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that CTC and ALP are the important biomarkers for the analysis of progression of breast cancer in females.

REFERENCES:

- Gauthier H, Guilhaume MN, Bidard FC, Pierga JY, Girre V, Cottu PH, Laurence V, Livartowski A, Mignot L, Dieras V: Survival of breast cancer patients with meningeal carcinomatosis. *Ann Oncol*. 2010, 21: 2183-2187. 10.1093/annonc/mdq232.
- Harris L, Fritsche H, Mennel R, Norton L, Ravdin P, Taube S, Somerfield MR, Hayes DF, Bast RC: American Society of Clinical Oncology 2007 update of recommendations for the use of tumor markers in breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 2007, 25: 5287-5312. 10.1200/JCO.2007.14.2364.
- Pierga JY, Deneux L, Bonneton C, Vincent-Salomon A, Nos C, Anract P, Magdelenat H, Pouillart P, Thiery JP: Prognostic value of cytokeratin 19 fragment (CYFRA 21-1) and cytokeratin-positive cells in bone marrow samples of breast cancer patients. *Int J Biol Markers*. 2004, 19: 23-31.
- Ohyama C, Hosono M, Nitta K, et al: Carbohydrate structure and differential binding of prostate specific antigen to Maackia amurensis lectin between prostate cancer and benign prostate hypertrophy. *Glycobiology* 14: 671-679, 2004.
- Hynes RO: Integrins: bidirectional, allosteric signaling machines. *Cell* 110: 673-687, 2002
- Taniguchi A, Hioki M and Matsmoto K: Transcriptional regulation of human ST4GalIV gene in testis and ovary cell line. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 301: 764-768, 2003.
- Christie DR, Shaikh FM, Lucas JA IV, Lucas JA III and Bellis SL: ST6Gal-I expression in ovarian cancer cell promotes an invasive phenotype by altering integrin glycosylation and function. *J Ovarian Res* 1: 3-10, 2008.
- Zhu Y, Srivatana U, Ullah A, Gagneja H, Berenson CS and Lance P: Suppression of a sialyltransferase by antisense DNA reduces invasiveness of human colon cancer cells in vitro. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1536: 148-160, 2001
- Takano R, Muchmore E, Dennis JW. Sialylation and Malignant Potential in Tumor-Cell Glycosylation Mutants. *Glycobiology*. 1994;4(5):665-674.
- Sawada M, Moriya S, Saito S, Shineha R, Satomi S, Yamori T, Tsuruo T, Kannagi R, Miyagi T. Reduced sialidase expression in highly metastatic variants of mouse colon adenocarcinoma 26 and retardation of their metastatic ability by sialidase overexpression. *IntJCancer*. 2002;97(2):180-185.